

**ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE SURVEYS IN EDUCATIONAL
MANAGEMENT RESEARCHES****Jose A. Tabulao**

Teacher III/Teacher-in-Charge, Cagdara-o Elementary School, Philippines

Rea S. Carangian

Teacher I, Gulap Elementary School, Philippines

Levy M. Soriano

Teacher III, Bagong Buhay B Integrated School, Philippines

Jayvee O. Bastasa

Teacher III, President Diosdado Macapagal High School, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Online surveys were the product of technological innovation in the development of scholarly work such as research works. This study examined the advantages, challenges and strategies in using online surveys in administering educational management researches. The study employed a descriptive research design which was participated by 200 randomly selected public school teachers among the selected public secondary schools in the Philippines. The study used a researcher-made survey-questionnaire as the main research instrument. The study found out that online surveys were highly advantageous in the administration of educational researches in terms of accessibility, cost-effectiveness and speed of data collection. However, teachers encountered different challenges in using online surveys such as low-response rate, digital divide respondents and question misinterpretation. Thus, the study further revealed that teachers used incentives, pre-testing surveys and follow-up reminders as effective strategies in using online surveys when conducting educational management researches.

Keywords:

assessing, impact, online, survey, advantage, challenges, strategies, accessibility, low-response, incentives

INTRODUCTION

Data collection procedure is one of the critical aspects in writing and completing a research work. This involves herculean tasks where the researchers administer their research instrument in order to gather and collect raw data from their targeted respondents. Data collection is also viewed as the dynamic process in a research because it involves scientific processes in collecting, organizing and preparing the raw data for data analysis. In writing a research work, data collection and data gathering procedure are used interchangeably but the content and aspects including its technical processes are similar. The core component of data collection procedure is the detail and scientific presentation how the researcher gather the data. In this line, data sources are one of very critical aspect in research writing which emanates from proper and scientifically-made data collection procedure. Apparently, data gathering procedures and data collection procedure does not only involve series of tasks. In a highly comprehensive and intricate researches, data collection commonly designed based on the time frame and the availability of the targeted respondents. In addition, data collection processes also involves certain amount of money which is to be used for funding researcher's daily subsistence while conducting his or her research work. Commonly, data collection procedure among researches which have larger scope and larger number of respondents require serious amount of time and efforts where the researchers physically administer his or her researcher instrument. In the most progressive trend in data collection, online survey has also become a current resurfacing trend. In this data collection method, the researcher uses an online application or tool where he or she transfers his or her survey-questionnaire into the form. As such, the link generated from the

form is set to be sent among the targeted respondents of a certain research work. In the context of academic institutions in the Philippines, online survey has been widely recognized and adopted during the time of pandemic. As physical interaction is limited during the pandemic, researchers are able to continue their research work by bringing data collection procedure into technological platform. Commonly used online survey tool is Google Form where researchers transfer their developed research instrument into the platform and such link is sent to the respondents. Notably, online survey is gradually adapted even after the pandemic, researcher finds online survey through the use of technological platform as convenient and practical. In this regard, they also find online survey as a platform where they can actually gather data without requiring their physical presence on the exact locale and interact physically with their respondents. However, this current paper's researchers observed that online surveys become an excuse just to facilitate data collection procedure easily. Also, as the researchers also observed, online surveys are taken for granted because researchers tend to choose online surveys even if the locale and respondents are residing nearby or within their reach. In other words, online surveys are used even if the locale and respondents are easily reached. This paves the interests of the researcher to closely assess the effectiveness of online surveys in conducting educational management researches. Surrounding the interests of the researchers is that they also observed that online surveys are used even in the most critical and confidential aspect of their study specifically when conducting educational management researches. Along this line, when conducting online surveys under educational management researchers, teacher-researchers are given so much leverage to facilitate their research instrument without formally seeking the permission of school heads and officials under a certain division. This condition directly defeats the intent of data collection procedure. Following this condition, the researchers find it necessary to assess online surveys effectiveness, challenges and strategies used by teachers in conducting educational management researches.

Early responders and late responders on online surveys reflect different segments of data collection procedure which directly affect the timeliness and accuracy of a research work. Systematic biases are also found in using online surveys in researches as it exhibits potential bias and inaccurate responses from the research's respondents (Estelami 2014). There is an established methodology for conducting survey research that aimed to ensure rigorous research and robust outputs. With the use of easy-to-use online survey forms most researchers are now inclined in using online surveys. However, the quality of survey studies has declined (Ball, 2019). Online survey research is used more frequently and better accepted by researchers. Yet, survey techniques are still regularly transformed by new technologies. Hence, adhering to a strong ethics code is vital to gain respondents' trust and to produce valid results (Evans & Mathur, 2018). Data is of paramount importance for research. Online surveys can be conducted at a low cost and in a short period. The researcher can start the survey, pause the survey and restart the survey whenever he wants. The challenges related to online surveys are the sampling response rate, non-respondent characteristics and maintenance of confidentiality (Kutscher & Eid, 2024). Questionnaire designs are being developed to improve the quality of online survey in research. Its element includes the increased or perceived social presence (Yoda, 2025). Based on previous studies cited in this paper, the researchers find out that knowledge gap exists on the basis that these studies purely concentrate on the concept and relative effects of online surveys on the credibility of a research work. Thus, this paper filled this knowledge gap as it assessed the effectiveness of online surveys in educational management researches as perceived by teachers among public secondary schools in the Philippines. Hence, this study supported Sustainable Development Goals-4 (Quality Education). As the study provided significant analysis on the effectiveness of online surveys, it may help teachers to carefully implement online surveys in conducting educational management researches which can eventually lead to the development of research practices in the field of education.

OBJECTIVES

This study assessed the effectiveness of online surveys in educational management researches based on the perceptions of public secondary school teachers among the selected schools in the Philippines. Specifically, this paper answered the following questions:

1. How may teachers' perceptions on the effects of online surveys in the administration of educational researches be assessed in terms of:
 - 1.1 accessibility;
 - 1.2 cost-effectiveness; and
 - 1.3 speed of data collection?
2. How may the challenges encountered by the teachers in using online surveys in the administration of educational researches be assessed in terms of:

- 2.1 response rate;
- 2.2 digitalization; and
- 2.3 question interpretation?
3. How may effective strategies used by teachers in using online surveys when conducting educational management researches be assessed in terms of:
 - 3.1 incentives;
 - 3.2 pre-testing; and
 - 3.3 reminders?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive research in order to assess the effectiveness of online surveys in educational management researches based on the perceptions of public secondary school teachers among the selected schools in the Philippines. The study was participated by 200 randomly selected public secondary school teachers. The study used simple random sampling in selecting the respondents of the study. The developed survey-questionnaire was utilized. This contained three (3) parts whereas it also subjected to validation and internal consistency measure. As to the construction of the researcher-made survey-questionnaire, part 1 contained items relating to the teachers' perceptions on the effects of online surveys in the administration of educational researches while part 2 contained items relating to the challenges encountered by teachers in using online surveys in the administration of educational researches. Thus, part 3 contained items relating to the effective strategies used by teachers in using online surveys when conducting educational management researches. On one hand, expertise of validators was sought where this was composed by three (3) Graduate School professors holding expertise on educational management and research writing. They marked that researcher-made survey-questionnaires as "excellent." On one hand, reliability test through pilot test was made whereas the developed questionnaire obtained a Cronbach Alpha result of .817, signified that the instrument was acceptable. Thus, 4-Likert Scale was used. For part 1, it used a 4-Likert Scale such as: 4-Highly Effective, 3-Effective, 2-Slightly Effective and 1-Not Effective. For items under part 2 similar scale was used but with different verbal descriptions such as: 4-Always Encountered, 3-Encountered, 2-Often Encountered and 1-Not Encountered. Then, similar scale used in part 1 was also used on items under part 3. As to the data collection procedure, the researchers used Google Form in order to facilitate their survey-questionnaire. Link was sent to the respondents' email addresses which was requested by the researchers. Then, when all the data have been collected, the researcher organized and applied relevant statistical tools. Apparently, the researchers applied frequency, mean and general weighted mean as relevant statistical tools. In addition, the researchers complied with highest ethical protocols in the conduct of independent research study which included the provision of informed consent, short orientation where the researchers discussed the nature and intent of the study and proper storage and deletion of the gathered raw data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the post-pandemic educational landscape and research development, online surveys emerged as a primary platform in educational management research specifically in the context of data collection procedure. This approach has been widely adapted and recognized by Higher Education Institution specially under the Graduate Schools across the country. In this line, an increased in the accessibility in internet connection and digital platforms enabled teacher-researchers to facilitate online surveys. It is then, a scientific necessity to comprehensively the effectiveness of online surveys in conducting educational management researches.

1. **Perceptions on the Effects of Online Surveys in the Administration of Educational Management Researches.** The results showed that accessibility obtained the highest mean score of 3.78, described as highly effective while cost-effectiveness gained a mean score of 3.67, also described as highly effective. Also, speed of data collection obtained a mean score of 3.64, described as highly effective. This implied that teachers' perceived the use of online surveys as highly effective as they are significantly accessible. The results also implied that digital format of surveys allowed for easier and practical participation of the targeted respondents in a certain educational management research. Thus, online surveys enabled broader range of participation where teacher-researchers viewed this as significant mechanism to extract varied responses from their targeted respondents. On one hand, the

result of cost-effectiveness variable showed that teachers perceived online surveys also as highly effective. This revealed that online surveys minimize significant expenses shouldered by the teacher-researchers when conducting educational management researches. This also showed that cost-effectiveness of online surveys not only benefits researchers but also enabled more frequent and extensive data collection. Lastly, the result on speed of data collection variable showed that teachers perceived online surveys as highly effective. This meant that through the use of online surveys in educational management researches, there were able to facilitate their data collection easily thereby, facilitating immediate analysis and feedback to the data collected. These results supported the study of Wu et al. (2022) which revealed that online surveys clearly defined accurate data collection, refined population response and positively implicated the efficient and speedy data collection in any researches under diverse field of interests. The study implicated that there should be proper training and workshops for the teacher-researchers to better facilitate and use online surveys for educational management researches.

2. **Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Using Online Surveys in the Administration of Educational Management Researches.** The results showed teachers always encountered low response rate ($w_m=3.56$), digitally divide respondents ($w_m=3.41$) and question misinterpretation ($w_m=3.39$) when using online surveys in administering educational management researches. These results showed that teachers always encountered low response rates when floating online surveys. This posed critical concerns in data collection as low response rates could compromise the validity and reliability of research findings as perceived by the teacher-researchers. Factors emanating from low response rates when using online surveys were survey fatigue, lack of time among the targeted respondents and insufficient motivation to participate in research activities imposed to the targeted respondents. On one hand, the result on digital divide implied that teachers always encountered this challenge. Disparities in access to technology and internet connectivity were common reasons why most the targeted respondents failed to fill or accomplish online surveys. To this effect, teacher-researchers also perceived that respondents in urban areas may have reliable internet access and digital literacy while those in rural areas may struggle in accessing reliable internet connectivity and digital literacy. Lastly, results on question misinterpretation as always encountered by the teacher-researchers implied that misinterpretation arose from unclear wording, ambiguous questions or a lack of context leading to inaccurate responses. Target-respondents were able to clarify such questions because of the lack of personal interaction to the teacher-researchers. Results of the study supported the study of Roberts and Allen (2015) which showed that use of online surveys posed different concerns such as privacy anonymity, low response rate and failure to gather responses from digitally-challenged areas. Similar study also revealed that analysis and reporting research findings posed reliability and accuracy concerns. The study implicated that teacher-researchers should improve their competence in using online surveys. Provide their respondents with equitable access to technology and select respondents who have reliable access to internet connectivity before using online surveys in conducting educational management researches.
3. **Effective Strategies Used by Teachers in Using Online Surveys.** The results showed that incentives obtained a mean score of 3.87, described as highly effective while pretesting and reminders both obtained mean scores of 3.81, both described as highly effective. The results showed that teachers perceived provision of incentives as highly effective strategy. This implied that teachers encouraged the participation of their targeted respondents in online surveys by giving small tokens, monetary rewards, gifts or professional development opportunities. This also showed that this strategy increase respondents' motivation to accomplish online surveys. Thus, provision of incentives made by the teacher-respondents served as a gratuitous gesture in recognition to the time and efforts laid by their respondents. Meanwhile, the result on pretesting variable showed that teachers perceived this strategy as highly effective provided that they conducted trial run on the online survey developed with small group of participants before full administration to the actual respondents. This signified that teacher-researchers enabled to identify potential issues related to question clarity and survey length. Apparently, teachers perceived pretesting as highly effective strategies as mean to improve the quality of the data collection process as they administered educational management researches. Lastly,

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reminders variable also perceived as highly effective strategies where teacher-researchers sent reminders to teachers about the survey which could significantly boost response rates. In this line, reminders could be communicated through email, text messages or even social media accounts of the targeted respondents. Results of the study supported the study of Sammut et al. (2021) which showed that utmost care in accessing the respondents, contacting target sample several times, adjusting duration of fieldwork, informing respondents in advance and the use of rewards were the most highly effective strategies when using online surveys.

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CONCLUSION

Online surveys were the product of technological innovation in the development of scholarly work such as research works. Conclusively, the study found out that online surveys were highly effective in the administration of educational researches in terms of accessibility, cost-effectiveness and speed of data collection. However, teachers encountered different challenges in using online surveys such as low-response rate, digital divide respondents and question misinterpretation. Thus, the study further revealed that teachers used incentives, pre-testing surveys and follow-up reminders as effective strategies in using online surveys when conducting educational management researches.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ball, H. L. (2019). Planning the online survey. *Conducting Online Surveys*, 14–32. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781506335186.n2>
- [2] Estelami, H. (2014). The effects of survey timing on student evaluation of teaching measures obtained using online surveys. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 37(1), 54–64. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0273475314552324>
- [3] Evans, J. R., & Mathur, A. (2018). The value of online surveys: A look back and a look ahead. *Internet Research*, 28(4), 854–887. <https://doi.org/10.1108/intr-03-2018-0089>
- [4] Kutscher, T., & Eid, M. (2024). Psychometric benefits of self-chosen rating scales over given rating scales. *Behavior Research Methods*, 56(7), 7440–7464. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-024-02429-w>
- [5] Roberts, L. D., & Allen, P. J. (2015). Exploring ethical issues associated with using online surveys in educational research. *Educational Research and Evaluation*, 21(2), 95–108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803611.2015.1024421>
- [6] Sammut, R., Griscti, O., & Norman, I. J. (2021). Strategies to improve response rates to web surveys: A literature review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 123, 104058. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2021.104058>
- [7] Wu, M.-J., Zhao, K., & Fils-Aime, F. (2022). Response rates of online surveys in published research: A Meta-analysis. *Computers in Human Behavior Reports*, 7, 100206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbr.2022.100206>
- [8] Yoda, F. S. (n.d.). *The Influence of Online Survey Design on Data Quality in Social Science and Consumer Behavior Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.11606/t.12.2025.tde-31102025-163025>